

Optimal isochromat frequencies for T2* spin-level simulation

Introduction

Simulation plays an important role in MRI development, research, and education [1], especially at the spin level, since this type of simulation captures more faithfully the physical phenomena. Some tissue parameters are well modeled and easy to simulate (i.e., the density and T2 or T1). But simulating T2* is particularly challenging because it depends on local micro variations of the magnetic field. To accurately represent T2* decay many isochromats per location are required, increasing the computational load. This is true for simulations in the “isochromat domain” or Bloch or spin-level simulations and for the “Fourier domain”, such as Extended Phase Graphs. Here we only focus on spin-level simulations.

We propose a mechanism for optimally choosing the position, number, and frequency of the isochromats for obtaining a signal which represents well the T2* decay.

Methods

When the frequencies of the isochromats for a given location follow a Lorentzian distribution, the signal has an exponential decay with T2*. First, we propose an optimal sampling of this distribution to reduce the required number of isochromats. Secondly, we propose to jointly consider the sampling in space (typical to spin-level simulations) with the sampling in frequency (needed for T2* decay).

Frequency sampling

We find how to sample the Lorentzian distribution to minimize the number of required spins. We choose M frequencies ω that best approximate the expected FID signal, $S(t)$, by minimizing the Mean Square Error (MSE) between $S(t)$ and $S_{\omega}(t)$ at N time samples (N=100 is enough).

We optimized only once for a fixed width of the Lorentzian distribution [2], and the M frequencies are scaled to find them for other widths.

Spatial dependence

A typical simulation will use several spins located more densely than the expected resolution of the reconstruction. A direct solution for adding T2* decay would require locating M isochromats (with the frequencies found in the previous section) at each spin location. Here we experiment with the idea of using a different random subset of $L \leq J$ isochromat frequencies at each location. The rationale is that the values associated to the pixels will be obtained by some averaging, and therefore they will include information from many different frequencies.

We assume that the number of spins is J times larger than the expected number of pixels in each dimension. For each spin location we use L frequencies (in 2D, $L \cdot J^2$ spins per pixel). To simulate a generic sequence, for each time instant we average the signal by convolving it with a sinc function adapted to the pixel size. This filtered signal is then sampled at the pixel locations, and ρ and T2* are estimated: ρ as the value of the signal for $t=0$, and T2* by fitting an exponential decay to the signal.

We did the simulations in 1D and 2D, employing known objects with different ρ and T2*. We tried different combinations of J (spatial positions) and L (frequencies). We computed the MSE and the relative MSE of the T2* values.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows (left) the optimal 11 frequencies (up), the location of uniformly sampling the cumulative distribution function (Deterministic) with 11 (middle) and 21 frequencies (down). The simulated signal (right) for 11 optimized frequencies has a better fit than the deterministic 11 frequencies (MSE is 35%). For comparison, to obtain a similar fit, 21 deterministic frequencies would be needed.

Fig. 2 shows a 1D phantom with the true ρ and $T2^*$ and the estimations from the simulation, showing a good match for a total of 44 isochromats per pixel.

Fig. 3 shows the error in $T2^*$ for different J and L in the 1D phantom. As expected, the more isochromats used in the simulation the better the estimation of $T2^*$. Interestingly, the error is relatively independent of how they are distributed between space and frequency. For this phantom an average of 33 isochromats per pixel gives errors of only 15%, considering the high interpixel variability.

Fig. 4 shows a 2D phantom, showing a good match for a total of 176 ($4 \times 4 \times 11$) isochromats per pixel. We also show the signal from the simulation (blue dots), the exponential fit (red line) and the theoretical decay (green line) and a profile for ρ and $T2^*$ fit.

Conclusions

Our method reduces the number of the isochromats needed for obtaining a signal which represents well the $T2^*$ decay, better than a deterministic sampling of the Lorentzian distribution. The frequencies need to be computed only once for a given number of isochromats.

References

- [1] C. Castillo-Passi, R. Coronado, G. Varela-Mattatall, C. Alberola-López, R. Botnar, P. Irarrazaval. KomaMRI.jl: An Open-source Framework for General MRI Simulations with GPU acceleration. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*, 90(1):329-342, 2023.
- [2] Z. Liang and P. Lauterbur. *Principles of Magnetic Resonance Imaging: A Signal Processing Perspective*. IEEE Press series in biomedical engineering. SPIE Optical Engineering Press, 2000.

(a)

(b)

Captions:

Figure 1: (a) Isochromat frequencies, (b) Correspondent signal obtained (blue) compared with ideal FID signal (orange) for global optimization with $M=11$ (upper row), deterministic frequencies with $M=11$ (middle row) and $M=21$ (bottom row).

Figure 2: 1D simulation with $M=L=11$, $J=4$. ρ and $T2^*$ phantom (blue line) and simulation (orange o).

Figure 3: $T2^*$ relative error in percentage between 1D phantom of Fig. 2 and simulation as a function of J and L for $M=11$. $JL=C$ plotted for reference.

Figure 4: 2D simulation in 2D. (a) ρ and $T2^*$ phantom with two singular points marked in red and blue; (b) Simulation; (c) Signal (blue line), fitting (red), and theoretical decay (black) for red point in (a); (d) Same for blue point in (a); (e) Profiles of ρ and $T2^*$ for the central row of the phantom.